

COMPOSITE LAMINATE APPLICATIONS IN MAGNETIC FUSION

ENERGY SUPERCONDUCTING MAGNET SYSTEMS*

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Potential composite applications span the range from industrial laminates to advanced composites. Service conditions are unusually demanding, as materials must function predictably over a 20-year lifetime at 4.2 kelvin while subject to neutron and gamma radiation. Laminate components must also withstand occasional warming to room temperature. Presently, industrial laminates of the NEMA/ASTM G-10 or G-11 types are most frequently proposed for electrical and thermal insulation. This reflects the low cost, ready availability and successful use of such materials in existing small superconducting magnets. However, the more stringent demands of MFE systems requires the development of component-specified industrial laminates, thoroughly tested under radiation and cryogenic conditions. Present designs do not make structural use of advanced composite laminates. However, the combination of high modulus, low thermal and electrical conductivity make such materials attractive substitutes for stainless steel in some components of superconducting magnets. Advanced-composite metal-matrix technology has an important role to play in understanding the effects of cyclic stress on the current-carrying ability of the metallic superconducting composite.

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Introduction

It is not unreasonable to believe that, by the middle of the next century, a large proportion of our electrical energy will be produced by huge fusion reactor power plants. In these plants, the reactions which power the sun itself will be harnessed. Unlike the fission reactors of today, the fusion plant will "burn" atoms from water and produce nonradioactive helium gas. It cannot "run away" or "melt down". It has been estimated that the fusion energy available from one barrel of water is equal to 720 barrels of fuel oil or 240 tons of coal.

In the scientific community, there is a worldwide, massive effort underway to understand the fusion process and to design and build devices which will be the forerunners of fusion reactors. It is a project which should be of greatest concern to anyone who feels that a dependable supply of energy is essential for long term survival of mankind.

It seems almost certain that the reacting material in these plants, the plasma, will be confined by the use of magnetic fields produced by enormous superconducting coils operating at temperatures near that of liquid helium. At these temperatures the superconductors carry very high magnet currents without loss. The two most promising candidates for magnetic confinement devices are the tokamak system illustrated in Figure 1 and the magnetic mirror system illustrated in Figure 2. The immense size of these reactors can be appreciated by comparison with the standard two-meter men in the illustrations. Such power plants will probably not become realities until after the turn of the century. They will be the culmination of a step-by-step approach to solving of problems arising from both the physics of the reaction process and from demands made on materials from which reactors must be constructed.

There are members of the scientific and technical community who believe that the materials problems are so severe as to preclude development of a practical MFE reactor. There is some justification for this pessimism, considering that a plasma heated to $\sim 50 \times 10^6$ °C must exist in close proximity to superconducting magnets which are maintained at liquid helium temperature while subjected to neutron and gamma radiation. The cost effective lifetime of a reactor is estimated at 20 years. It is reasonable to conclude that the materials problems presented by MFE systems will challenge the technology and the ingenuity of materials scientists for years to come. In this paper, we examine the extent to which composite laminate materials technology can alleviate problems which arise within the cryogenic portions of proposed reactor systems. In addition to the various magnet systems identified in Figure 1, the cryogenic portion of a tokamak reactor also includes the central toroidal magnet support column.

Figure 1. Tokamak power plant designed by the Princeton Plasma Physics Laboratory.

Figure 2. Magnetic mirror power reactor design proposed by the Lawrence Livermore Laboratory.

We begin by reviewing the proposed use of laminates in current MFE reference designs and continue with a discussion of where advanced-composite laminates might make significant contributions in future designs. We briefly review the present state of knowledge of the performance of composite laminates at cryogenic temperatures and present a short discussion of the direction being taken by current research programs in addressing the immediate needs of the MFE community.

Composite Applications in Reference System Designs

Reference designs such as illustrated in Figures 1 and 2 are concepts of how a practical MFE power plant might look if it were built with the current knowledge of the physics of the reaction and of material properties. The objective is to define major problem areas and to direct attention to their solution.

In current reference designs, nonmetallic composites are primarily specified for electrical or thermal insulation applications, with structural functions being of secondary importance. The possibility of combining electrical insulation with structural support is recognized in all designs. However, it is generally believed that the magnet stresses will be too high for adequate strain limitation by the low-modulus insulators under consideration. Interest in metal-matrix laminate technology is presently confined to the superconducting composite.

Electrical Insulators

The primary application is turn-to-turn, interlayer or pancake-to-pancake insulation between the superconductor bundles. The insulation is frequently segmented to provide cooling passages for liquid helium. Finished laminates are frequently used with punched-out channel slots. In some designs, the superconducting cables are spiral-wrapped with B-staged glass-epoxy tape, leaving channels for cooling. The tape must cure at a low temperature and under low pressure. In other designs, the superconductor is supported in a U-shaped glass-epoxy channel section or wrapped around an internal glass-epoxy support as illustrated in Figure 3. As much as 800-1000 metric tons of laminate material might be required for electrical insulation in the magnet systems of a commercial MFE power station.

Figure 3. Proposed use of glass-epoxy laminates for superconductor coil forms.

The insulating laminates are usually referred to very generically as G-10, Micarta, glass-epoxy, etc., reflecting the generally satisfactory use of this type of material in small superconducting magnets. However, the high penalties paid for insulation

failure in large magnets and the additional requirement of long life in a radiation environment will require much more control over the materials used in MFE applications. All designers express concern over adverse effects of radiation; some consider that radiation damage might preclude all organic materials from MFE superconducting magnet systems.

Thermal Insulation

Standoffs are required to support and to thermally isolate the cryogenic structure from the surrounding warm environment. Primary support points in a tokamak system are the base of the central column ($\sim 4.5 \times 10^5$ kg) and the individual supports for the large, toroidal superconducting magnets ($\sim 1.6 \times 10^4$ kg). Conventional industrial laminates will probably suffice for this purpose, as radiation is not expected to be a factor. Some designers have suggested constructing the central toroidal magnet support column of glass-epoxy industrial laminate which would also serve as the coil form on which circumferential magnets would be wound. This would be a massive structure on the order of 8 meters height by 2 meters in diameter. The large compressive force exerted on the column by the toroidal coils poses a problem. It has been estimated that a glass-epoxy column with a wall thickness of 28 cm would adequately sustain the imposed load but would very likely undergo excessive deflection.

Failure of two adjacent toroidal coils results in a very large overturning moment which must be resisted by a provisional support system. Most tokamak designs envision an individual dewar for each coil, requiring that the support structure pass through the dewar walls. One proposed solution is to attach a large number of glass-epoxy struts to one dewar wall, the struts contacting the opposite wall only in event of a fault. This application alone is estimated to consume about 16 metric tons of laminate in a commercial reactor.

Nonmetallic Dewars

It is probable that the physics of plasma containment will require that some of the superconducting magnets operate in a pulsed mode. There is concern that the changing electromagnetic fields will produce eddy current heating in nearby metallic structures and substantially increase the cost of refrigeration required to maintain the superconductors in their operating temperature range. The inner wall of the magnet dewar would be a major source of such losses if made of stainless steel. This has led several designers to propose making the wall of nonmetallic laminate. As schematically illustrated in Figure 4, the inner wall may also have to serve as the liquid helium container, requiring that the laminate be impervious to helium. Although small, nonmetallic helium dewars have been in use for some time, relatively little is known about the factors controlling helium permeability through laminates at 4 kelvin. It may be necessary to incorporate a thin stainless steel liner in the laminate as a permeability barrier. The pulsed magnetic field also subjects

Figure 4. Proposed use of a nonmetallic laminate as a liquid helium container and inner dewar wall. The cables would be cooled by force-flow helium.

the dewar wall to cyclic stresses, requiring that the selected laminate be fatigue resistant. The laminate must also resist degradation from the existing radiation fluence. It would be desirable to have the inner dewar wall as stiff as possible to assist in limiting the strain in the superconducting cables.

Superconducting Composites

The current-carrying elements in a superconducting magnet are filaments of compounds such as NbTi or Nb₃Sn embedded in a high-conductivity, normal metal matrix, usually OFHC copper. It is therefore a metal-matrix composite, differing from a structural metal-matrix composite only in that the filaments are basically uniaxial (although transposed to reduce a.c. losses) and in that the functional parameter is current conduction rather than strength. The function of the copper matrix is to provide a shunt for the current in the event that a localized portion of the superconducting compound goes normal and to conduct the heat away rapidly enough to allow the superconductor to recover from the disturbance. The matrix is therefore referred to as the superconductor stabilizer. A secondary function of the matrix is to stiffen the composite, reducing strain in the superconducting filaments.

The term "composite" has several connotations in superconducting technology. A large number of superconducting filaments co-drawn with the stabilizing matrix forms a superconducting composite wire. Such wires are bundled to form a superconducting cable composite. Cables are wound on a form with appropriate

insulation to create a superconducting coil composite. A cross-section of such a composite is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Typical cross-section through a NbTi superconducting coil composite. Each bundle contains 180 NbTi filaments.

Energizing a superconducting coil creates electromagnetic forces which impose hoop stresses on the conductors. As the current density is increased, a critical level is eventually reached at which the superconducting compound reverts to the normal conducting state, causing the magnet to "quench". Recently, it has been experimentally found that this critical current level can be strongly affected by the strain within the superconducting material (1,2). This is particularly a problem with the brittle Nb₃Sn compound where as little as 0.2% strain may significantly degrade the critical current.

A second deleterious effect of external strain is an increase in the resistivity of the stabilizing matrix due to cold work. This is particularly a problem in stress-cycled superconducting composites made with the ductile NbTi compound. The result is a

premature quenching of the magnet due to propagation of localized normal regions which would have recovered had the matrix maintained its low resistivity.

A third effect is that magnets sometimes undergo a series of quenches at low fields before attaining their designed operating field -- a phenomenon known as "training". This behavior bears a marked similarity to the "shakedown" phenomenon observed in conventional metal-matrix laminates subjected to fatigue (3). It seems likely that these two phenomena have a similar physical basis in readjustment of internal stresses. Thus far, studies of stress effects in superconductors have been primarily undertaken by low-temperature physicists working in isolation from the scientists addressing similar problems in structural composites. A combining of these two technologies should be very beneficial in solving mutual problems.

Overview of Current Composite Materials Problems

All current MFE reactors require the use of large tonnages of nonmetallic laminates which must perform their insulating and structural functions over a 20-year lifetime at liquid helium temperature while subjected to neutron and gamma radiation. The laminates must also withstand thermal cycling between 295 K and 4.2 K when the reactor is shut down for maintenance. It is widely thought that the required radiation resistance will prove to be the most intractable problem. Many scientists are concerned that the release of energy stored in organic laminates due to low-temperature radiation will destroy the materials when warmed to room temperature.

Present thinking on the types of nonmetallic laminates best suited for low-temperature radiation service is very generalized, reflecting how little is known on the subject. It is thought that epoxies will have the best radiation resistance when cured with an aromatic amine. The use of polyimide-glass laminates has also been suggested, as polyimide is about the most radiation resistant organic material presently available. It may be that laminates filled with granular alumina will have improved radiation tolerance. The radiation resistance of organic laminates will almost certainly affect reactor design, as the fluence at the magnets can be controlled at some cost by increasing the amount of shielding employed. Very likely, a balance will have to be achieved between materials cost and total reactor fabrication cost. As an order-of-magnitude estimate, current thinking sees the maximum total neutron fluence at the magnets over a 20-year lifetime at 10^{20} to 10^{22} n/m², depending on magnet location. The neutron flux creates secondary gamma radiation in the presence of iron or copper.

Problems in the superconducting composite technology are largely related to the effect of strain on superconductor performance and bear a similarity to shakedown problems which exist in structural metal-matrix laminates.

Future Composite Applications

Advanced composites could effectively be substituted for stainless steel in many components of present MFE superconducting magnet designs. Primary obstacles are cost, lack of design data and lack of design experience.

At the present time, the most attractive applications for high-modulus, polymer-matrix laminates are in the pulsed superconducting magnet systems of tokamak machines (poloidal coil system) (4). Here, nonmetallic structures may be mandatory to reduce eddy current losses while limiting strain in the superconductors. Coil forms, helium containers (inner dewar walls) and coil prestressing and stiffening elements could all benefit from high-modulus laminate construction. Conductor strain has not been a significant problem in existing small superconducting magnets; however, magnet stresses scale with magnet size for equal current densities. Conductor strain must be limited to acceptable values, as operating large magnets at less than their optimum current densities is not likely to be a practical alternative.

Perhaps the most straightforward application of advanced composites would be as prestressing bands to resist hoop stresses generated by the coils. Such bands could either be laminated into the coil composite during fabrication or applied as an external selective reinforcement. A basically uniaxial laminate should perform well in such an application. Graphite-reinforced polymers appear to be the most promising material. The high cost and the high neutron cross section of boron would likely limit its use to specialized applications where radiation fluence is low and where the very high compressive strength of boron-polymer laminates can be effectively utilized.

The need to limit superconductor strain in magnets subjected to very large electromagnetic stresses suggests the desirability of providing reinforcement as close to the superconducting filaments as possible. Ideally, one would reinforce the stabilizing material, provided that this could be done without degrading electrical conductivity. Theoretically, this could be accomplished by spacing reinforcing filaments at distances greater than the electronic mean free path of the stabilizer material at 4.2 kelvin (~ 0.01 mm for OFHC copper). Cursory experiments with boron fibers bonded into ultrapurity aluminum in the author's laboratory has shown that this principle is valid; however, obtaining proper filament spacing in a drawn superconductor wire is another matter. A more practical approach might be to selectively reinforce the superconducting wire composite with high-modulus fiber prior to bundling into cables. Again, it would seem that graphite would be the preferred material.

There are some in the scientific and technical community who believe that scarcity of alloying elements will limit the practicality of large MFE power plants. It has been estimated that a single station might require 50,000 tons of stainless steel just in the superconducting magnet systems if current design approaches are followed. The threat of such shortages will

cause designers to more seriously consider extensive composite construction. Certainly, filamentary-reinforced aluminum would be a viable substitute material.

Present State of Knowledge

The mechanical and thermal properties of composite laminates at cryogenic temperatures has been the subject of several recent reviews (5-7). Efforts to systematically expand the data base on advanced composite laminates have been reported (8). Available data justify optimism as to the future use of composites for cryogenic structures. Glass-reinforced laminates already have a favorable track record and cooling boron, graphite or aramid-reinforced epoxy laminates to cryogenic temperatures has usually been found to improve rather than degrade the mechanical properties. The few studies examining the effect of cryogenic temperatures on fatigue performance are likewise encouraging (9-11). The weight of experimental evidence suggests that many laminate matrix systems developed for room-temperature use also perform well at cryogenic temperatures. Flexibilized matrices may prove to be beneficial in angle-ply laminates subjected to fatigue; however this remains to be proven. Recent work in the author's laboratory has shown that even laminates made from one of the highest-modulus commercial graphite-epoxy prepregs (GY-70/934) performs well at 4 kelvin (12).

The cryogenic performance of uniaxial laminates of glass, graphite and boron-reinforced epoxies and of boron-reinforced aluminum are compared in terms of critical property ratios to that of 304 stainless steel in Figures 6 (a-d). Such ratios are useful for assessing material efficiency. Although this figure compares the most favorable orientation of laminates with that of annealed stainless steel (assuming welding would be required), the advantage of composite laminates in strength-, stiffness-, and weight-critical components is evident.

Very little is really known about the effect of cryogenic temperatures on the properties of high-pressure industrial laminates. The practical experience with such materials has been favorable, but restricted to comparatively noncritical applications. The situation with industrial laminates is complicated by the highly competitive nature of the laminating industry and the highly-proprietary nature of their products. NEMA/ASTM type laminates are produced to meet specific performance criteria at or near room temperature -- primarily electrical insulating criteria. Constituents are only broadly specified. Thus it is found that laminates of the same NEMA designation produced by different manufacturers have significantly different cryogenic properties.

At the present time, superconducting composites using NbTi as the conductor are well developed commercial products. Composites using Nb₃Sn are commercially available but are still under development, while those using V₃Ga as the conductor are in the

(a) Ratio of tensile yield strength to density.

(b) Ratio of Young's modulus to density.

(c) Ratio of thermal conductivity to tensile yield strength.

(d) Ratio of thermal conductivity to Young's modulus.

Figure 6. Temperature dependence of critical property ratios for uniaxial composite laminates and for annealed stainless steel.

research stage. The maximum fields obtainable with these three types of conductors is about 8, 12 and 16 tesla, respectively.

Current Research Efforts

The only composite material effort currently directed specifically toward MFE problems is the establishment and characterization of a component-specified G-10 and G-11 type high-pressure industrial laminate for cryogenic use. NBS, working in cooperation with the Industrial Laminate Section of NEMA, has arranged for the commercial availability of such laminates, to be designated G-10CR and G-11Cr. The laminates selected for this purpose have a successful history of cryogenic use and are presently in

commercial production by one of the U.S. laminating firms. The complete manufacturing specifications for these laminates will be available to all U.S. manufacturers of laminates through the NEMA organization. The electrical, thermal, mechanical and radiation-affected properties of the laminates will be thoroughly documented from 295 K to 4 K. Additionally, the G-11CR formulation is being experimentally produced using boron-free glass reinforcement in an attempt to reduce low-temperature radiation damage.

While no advanced-composite studies are currently specifically directed toward MFE applications, considerable data of interest to the MFE community will be generated in a separate NBS program having the objective of developing the data required to construct a very lightweight superconducting magnet for use in a magneto-hydrodynamic or rotating cryogenic power supply (11). The weight restrictions dictate that the main magnet structure be fabricated with advanced composites. While the magnet will be far smaller than those proposed for MFE service, much of the data will be directly transferable.

The effect of stress on the electrical performance of superconducting wires is currently under intensive study in both the U.S. and in Europe. The primary effort is being directed toward understanding the electrical-mechanical relationship in commercial NbTi and Nb₃Sn composites, with the overall objective of developing more strain-tolerant superconductor composites.

Conclusions

The materials specialist working with magnetic fusion energy systems is confronted with a combination of problems rarely seen in any other technology. An economically viable MFE power plant will require that exceedingly complex structures perform their intended functions for 20 years while subject to continuous neutron and gamma radiation. A large part of the structure is required to be maintained at liquid helium temperature. Repair of structures which become defective may be impractical. The immense size of the proposed structures requires that the utmost care be exercised in selection of the structural materials and in fabrication methods. Pessimists emphasize the possibility that practical MFE power plants can never be built because of excessive demands on materials performance and likely shortages of critical alloying elements. It is a certainty that existing materials will be pushed to the limits of their performance and it may be that the ultimate feasibility of MFE power plants will be contingent on development of entirely new material systems.

This poses a particular challenge to the composite material systems. The immediate question is whether conventional, inexpensive high-pressure industrial laminates will be able to perform their insulating functions in MFE superconducting magnets or whether it will be necessary to develop specialized insulating laminates for this purpose. In the long run, it is anticipated that composites will be called upon to perform structural functions, particularly where problems of eddy current heating raises

the cost of refrigeration to unacceptable levels. It may be that laminates will have to also serve as liquid helium containers. The initial designs do not postulate the use of high-modulus composite materials. However, the very high stress levels in the superconducting magnets, coupled with the severe strain limitations on the conductors, necessitates stiffening of the magnet structure to an extent which might be achievable only by judicious use of advanced-composite technology. Finally, the superconducting composite itself provides a challenge to the composite materials specialist. The efficient functioning of very large magnets requires an understanding of both residual strain and externally-imposed strain on conductor performance and the eventual design of a superconducting composite which will permit the magnets to operate at their maximum efficiency. Close interaction between low-temperature physicists and specialists in metal-matrix composite technology is mandatory.

In the very long run, it may prove to be true that the alloying elements required to build a commercial-scale reactor using stainless steel as the primary cryogenic structural material will either be unavailable or will be excessively expensive. Should this happen, available data indicate that composite materials such as fiber-reinforced aluminum could serve as an acceptable substitute for cryogenic service.

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